

THE CUBAN MISSILE CRISIS (1962) AND THE WAR ON UKRAINE (2022): NUCLEAR THREAT 60 YEARS LATER

Carolina Ambinderⁱ

Vitelio Brustolinⁱⁱ

ABSTRACT

Between October 16 and 28, 1962, at the height of the Cold War, "thirteen days shook the world" with the US discovery of Soviet ballistic missiles, armed with nuclear warheads, being installed in Cuba. This episode, known as the "Cuban Missile Crisis," was the closest that humanity has come to a nuclear war in the last 60 years. However, the war in Ukraine, in which the current phase began with the Russian invasion at the end of February this year, has presenting successive threats of the use of nuclear weapons by Russia. More than half a century after the Cuban Missile Crisis, therefore, we are again experiencing a nuclear threat, highlighting discussions about the real effectiveness of International Law and the lessons that were *not* learned from previous conflicts.

BACKGROUND

With the end of the Second World War, it began the Cold War (1945 – 1991), a political, economic, ideological, and military global dispute between the United States of America (US) and the former Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR). In this context, already in 1949, the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) was found as the military alliance of the West. In addition, in the same year, the first Soviet atomic bomb was exploded, what the US was not expecting, at least not on that moment. Thus, it began the "greatest arms race of all time" (1).

In 1952, the first American hydrogen bomb was announced as an answer to the Soviet bomb, being it measured by the superior scale of megatons (one kiloton is equal to one thousand tons of TNT; one megaton is equal to one million tons of TNT). It is a bomb of nuclear fusion, also known as "thermonuclear bomb", which fusion is triggered by a nuclear fission (like Hiroshima and Nagasaki). Furthermore, in 1955, it was created the Warsaw Pact, the East military alliance, opposed to NATO. Therefore, the 1950's became known as the "nuclear years", because both US and the Soviet Union searched for even more weapons.

The main precedent of the Cuban Missile Crisis, though, would happen in the end of the decade. On January 1, 1959, through the Cuban Revolution, Fidel Castro took the power; consolidating the socialist regime in the country and making the US interrupt the diplomatic relations with Cuba. Here, it should be reminded the “Domino Theory”, in which a local incident might influence actors geographically close. In short, the Cuban Revolution turned on the American alert and, in practical terms, shifted the axle of the Cold War to the West.

In this sense, in 1961, trained by the Central Intelligence Agency (CIA), anti-Castro’s exiles landed in the Bay of Pigs, attempting to take out Fidel Castro. The expedition failed and resulted in the opposite original goal: it strengthened the relations between Cuban and the Soviet Union. In October of the following year, then, the CIA identified the installation of Soviet missiles in the Cuban territory, 145 kilometers from the Florida’s coast. This led the former US President, John F. Kennedy, to conclude that this was a plan of attack. This was the start of the tensest moment of the Cold War.

In an urgent Assembly called by the US at the Organization of the American States (OAS), the country obtained unanimous votes in favor of a naval blockade against Cuba (who was already expelled of the organization on that momentⁱⁱⁱ). The blockade was temporarily efficient, but the crisis was solved only after Kennedy’s acceptance on taking off the American missiles pointed to the Soviet Union in Turkey and Italy. In exchange, the Soviet leader, Nikita Khrushchev, agreed on removing the missiles in the Cuban territory and not putting others anymore. This agreement was secret by the time but end up revealed two decades later. In this way, in the beginning of November, the agreement between Kennedy and Khrushchev led to the removal of the Soviet missiles in Cuba.

FINDINGS

Although the US Armed Forces remained in readiness during the Cuban Missile Crisis, the situation was solved diplomatically, with a deal between the two parties and the use of International Law. In the first American claim, for example, it can be identified the right of defense and conservation: “(...) the State that feel threaded might, with no doubt, adopt in its territory or in its spheres of attribution, measures judged convenient to its defense, but it shall not go beyond, that is, it shall not invade the foreign sphere of attributions of other states or seek to impose its will on another State” (2)^v. Besides, the war blockade (adopted by the US in the naval field) is considered a pacific solution, even though not cordial, being defined as the “interruption through the armed force of a belligerent, of the communications between one port or ports, or other coasts part of the enemy and the high sea” (3)^v. It has yet the following conditions for being valid (i): the existence of a state of war; (ii) susceptible places to be blocked; (iii) declaration of a competent authority and the respective notification to the neutrals; and (iv) effectiveness. All these conditions were present in the referred blockade, including the involvement of OAS.

The Cuban Missile Crisis influenced the emerge of the expression “Mutual Assured Destruction” (M.A.D) still in the 1960`s, referring to the danger of the use of nuclear weapons by superpowers; after all, both had capacity for mutual annihilation. In this context, in 1968, it was introduced the United Nations Treaty on Non-Proliferation of Nuclear Weapons (NPT), valid since 1970. About Ukraine, on its turn, some facts are relevant to be mentioned, such as the country`s Independence on August 24, 1991 and the dissolution of the Soviet Union on December, 26, same year.

In 1990, the former president of US, George Bush, promised to the Russian leader, Mikhail Gorbachev, that NATO “would not move an inch to the east”, except for Germany, if this country was unified. This was a verbal promise, and it has been broken in large because both NATO and Russia have expansionist goals. The First War of Chechenia, from 1994 to 1996, in which more than 50 thousands of civilians were killed by Russia, was determinant for the Eastern European countries and NATO to get closer. The negotiations to the adherence of Czech Republic, Hungary, and Poland to NATO began in 1997 and got concrete in 1999, when these three countries joined the Organization. In 1999, it started the Second War of Chechenia, which last until 2009. On its turn, between 2004 and 2009, it was the time of Slovakia, Bulgaria, Romania, and all Eastern European countries to join NATO. Besides, during this period, it also occurred the adherence of three former soviet republics: Estonia, Latvia, and Lithuania (4).

In 1994, the Memorandum of Budapest assured the transfer of the nuclear arsenal of Ukraine, Belarus and Kazakhstan to Russia, with guarantees of security to these territories, sovereignty and political independence. The Memorandum was initially firmied by three nuclear superpowers: Russia, United States and United Kingdom. China and France signed it later, completing all the five permanent (“P5”) members of the UN`s Security Council (5).

Ukraine was invited to join NATO and, although this invitation is unfeasible since the War in Georgia (2008), Vladmir Putin claims that it represents a threat to Russia. After 2014, this membership got possible according to NATO`S rules, as Ukraine turned a territory in conflict because of the Russian annexation of Crimea and the civil war in Donbass. Nevertheless, soon after the annexation, the Ukrainian Parliament approved with a large majority a modification of the Constitution, considering joining the European Union and NATO as national goals. For some years already, then, Russia has seen threats to its territorial integrity and to its nation. This was the cause of Crimea annexation, for example, saying that an extremist power in the region would affect the Russian identity there (this annexation is not recognized by the international community). In this way, just as the Soviet Union claimed that the United States built a threatened situation in the Caribbean, leading to the Cuban Missile Crisis, Russia invaded Ukraine because of the perception of threat, mainly constituted by the non-compliance in the verbal promise of George Bush to Mikhail Gorbachev of not expanding NATO.

CONCLUSIONS

Despite the evolution of International Law and the recently six decades completed since the Cuban Missile Crisis, the War on Ukraine started with the disrespect of norms. According to the Charter of the United Nations Organization (UNO), it is prohibited aggression wars, wars of territory annexation and without the consent of the Security Council (SC), composed by the United States, Russia, China, United Kingdom, and France. Moreover, considering the article 27, III of the UN Charter, it should absent themselves of voting the members of the SC that are being part of a controversy that threatens the international peace (6). About the War on Ukraine, then, Russia not only invaded the country (disrespecting the Memorandum of Budapest and its content related to the protection of the Ukrainian territory and sovereignty), but also did not abstain itself in the SC, logically voting in favor of yourself and avoiding a resolution against the war. Russia disrespected the resolution of the International Court of Justice (UN's tribunal) too, in which the operations should have been suspended and the country should have unconditionally left Ukraine^{vi}. Adding a point, investigations increased about the practice of war crimes, like the intentional attack to Ukrainian civilian areas and installations, the military use of the nuclear plant of Zaporizhzhia and evidence of the execution of prisoners in cities like Bucha e Irpin, violating the Humanitarian International Law, especially the Hague and Geneva Conventions^{vii}.

The Russian threat of nuclear weapons use occurs since the beginning of the War on Ukraine in case the West made interventions. This has been happening through guns transfer and resources for the Ukraine armed forces, for example, but the threat did not get concrete, questioning the credibility of Putin's quotes. However, in September 2022, the Russian president made a threat of the use of tactical nuclear weapons, specifically, the ones with lower impact (from 0.5 to 5 kilotons), destructing targets like a vessel or a building. This strategy of Russia is an attempt to "scale for pacify" (7), but, in the meantime, the International Law and the central goal of peace keeping by UN are compromised.

SUGGESTIONS

The creation of the United Nations and its theoretical body for peace keeping, the Security Council, resulted from the context of the post-Second World War, wishing to avoid a new conflict and to give power of decision to its winners, respectively (see the UN'S Charter preamble). Therefore, after almost eighty years, a reform is necessary both in the SC and in the general structure of the UN. The international system passed by substantial modifications during these eight decades, practically in every segment: economy, politics, society, culture, communications, transport, weapons, Science, technology, etc. Besides, due to the main security topics discussed at the SC and the fact that the members have the veto power, the centrality of the body is demonstrating to be problematic. It is illegal that Russia had voted about a controversy where she is involved, but, in the invasions of Iraq and Afghanistan, for example, the United Nations and the United Kingdom should also have absented themselves. In

conclusion, article 27, III, from the UN's Charter, has been systematically unperformed since the 1950 decade.

Another consequence of the Second World War was the relative dimension of the space, as deterrence (the disincentive of a part in another's action) through the existence of nuclear weapons allows influence about events geographically distant. In this sense, theoretically, nuclear arsenals exist so they do not be use. Considering this topic between the Cold War superpowers – United States and the Soviet Union – countries that, together, hold 92% of the global nuclear power – it is crucial that agreements should be respected. Specifically, both the NPT and the “New Start” – New Strategic Arms Reduction Treaty (2011-2025) – that limits the quantity of ogives, platforms, and launches. United States, on its turn, make public its “nuclear triad”, consisted today by (i) 14 submarines with 240 ballistic missiles (SSBNs), enough fire power so only one of the submarines can be classified as the 6th most powerful nuclear element in the world; (ii) 400 terrestrial intercontinental ballistic missiles (ICBMs), under continuous alert since 1959; and (iii) 64 heavy bombers, capable of dropping bombs and cruise missiles with the flexibility of providing fire from anywhere in the world (8).

Finally, like in the Cuban Missile Crisis, the only plausible way out of the current conflict is through diplomacy, whose representatives and international organizations should invest more effort. After all, both the First and the Second World War, as well as the Cold War, are the history to be reminded, not repeated.

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ⁱ PhD Candidate in Strategic Studies of Defense and Security (Universidade Federal Fluminense/UFF) and Research Associate at InterAgency Institute (IA) and the Network of Future Seeds in Defense (Escola de Guerra Naval/EGN). carolina.ambinder@interagency.institute

ⁱⁱ Professor of International Relations at Universidade Federal Fluminense (UFF) and Researcher at Harvard University. <https://scholar.harvard.edu/brustolin>

ⁱⁱⁱ Cuba returned to OAS 2009.

^{iv} Free translation. Original text: “(...) o Estado que se sinta ameaçado poderá, sem dúvida, adotar, no seu território ou na esfera das suas atribuições, as medidas que julgue convenientes para a sua defesa, mas não deverá ir além, isto é, não deverá invadir a esfera de atribuições alheias ou procurar impor a sua vontade a outro Estado”.

^v Free translation. Original text: “interrupção, por meio da força armada de um beligerante, das comunicações entre um porto, ou portos, ou determinada parte das costas, do país inimigo e o alto mar”.

^{vi} Available at: <https://news.un.org/pt/story/2022/03/1783052>

^{vii} Available at: <https://newseu.cgtn.com/news/2022-06-16/UN-war-crimes-inquiry-collects-evidence-in-Buchan-and-Irpin-1aTuP4Gk0VO/index.html>

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